

Heterocyclic Quinones—Part III : Synthesis of Dialkylbenzodipyrrocolinequinones

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Manuscript received 9 August 1978, revised 21 August 1979, accepted 2 February 1982

A series of unsymmetrical dialkylbenzodipyrrocolinequinones has been synthesised by condensing chloranil with alkylpyridines giving both *trans* and *cis* forms of the compounds as evidenced through their elemental and spectral analysis.

In our previous communications¹⁻³ we described the synthesis of disubstituted benzo-dibenz-pyrrocolinequinones. A perusal of literature reveals that no work has been done on the reaction of chloranil with alkylpyridines. A reaction of 2,3-dichloro-1,4-naphthoquinone with α -picoline has been reported⁴. We now report the synthesis of some new dialkylbenzodipyrrocolinequinones (*trans* and *cis* forms) obtained by the condensation of chloranil with alkylpyridines (i.e. α -picoline, 2,4-lutidine, 2,6-lutidine). In the case of quinaldine and collidine no products could be isolated. This may be ascribed to steric effect.

The *trans* and *cis* structure of these quinones has been established on the basis of colour reaction with conc. H_2SO_4 ⁴. The compounds of *trans* configuration gave violet to blue coloured solution whereas those of *cis* configuration gave olive green to green solution with conc. H_2SO_4 . The ir spectra of these compounds showed characteristic bands at 1675 (C=O), 1315 cm^{-1} (C-N).

The uv spectra of both *trans* and *cis* structures showed the presence of three prominent absorption maxima. As expected, the *trans* isomers show absorption at longer wavelengths as compared to the corresponding *cis* isomers (Table 1).

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. UV absorption spectra of these compounds were recorded on a Beckman spectrophotometer, Model DU-2, using 1 cm path length quartz cells. IR spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord model-577 using KBr disc. The procedure for the preparation of substituted benzo-dipyrrocolinequinones is described below.

Chloranil (1 mol) was taken in 50 ml DMF. Alkyl pyridine (2 mol) was added slowly to this in a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was boiled under reflux on a water bath for 4 hr and then the solution was allowed to stand overnight. The product (*trans* form) separated, was filtered,

washed several times with small portions of ethanol, then with ether and dried. The filtrate was concentrated and water was added to it till the solution was turbid. The product (*cis* form) was obtained. It was filtered and washed with hot water, ethanol, ether and dried. Both forms of the compounds were recrystallised from desired solvent. The analysis, m.p., etc. are given in Table 1.

Mechanism: The reaction sequence for the formation of these compounds may be explained as: (1) quaternisation of the alkylpyridine with chloranil to give A [rendering the methyl group (R_2) more reactive], (2) A now gets cyclized to B by the elimination of HCl as shown below:

The *trans* structures provide larger scope for electronic excitation as compared to the *cis* structures as shown below which explains their absorption at longer wavelengths.

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED BENZO-DIPYRROCOLINE QUINONES*

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	Form of compd.	Recrystallization solvent	% Analysis		UV spectra	
						Calcd.	Found	DMF	log ε
								λ _{max} nm	
1.	H	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂	<i>Cis</i>	Acetone	C, 75.5	75.2	329	3.87
						H, 3.4	3.8	357	4.05
						N, 9.7	9.5	475	4.10
				<i>Trans</i>	Benzene	C, 75.5	75.4	335	3.91
						H, 3.4	3.4	351	4.15
						N, 9.4	9.6	581	4.25
2.	H	OH ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	<i>Cis</i>	Acetone +	C, 76.4	76.4	324	3.96
						H, 4.4	4.2	350	4.07
						N, 8.9	8.8	467	4.15
				<i>Trans</i>	Benzene	C, 76.4	76.2	330	3.87
						H, 4.4	4.4	347	4.10
						N, 8.9	8.9	575	4.21
3.	OH ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	<i>Cis</i>	Acetone	C, 76.4	76.3	320	3.85
						H, 4.4	4.4	366	4.15
						N, 8.9	8.7	463	4.13
				<i>Trans</i>	Benzene	C, 76.4	76.4	339	3.90
						H, 4.4	4.1	355	4.21
						N, 8.9	8.6	587	4.49

* Both the isomers do not melt upto 380°.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head of Chemistry Department for necessary facilities and to the U. G. C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (R. P. S.).

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